

interstore

D3.2 – Report on the Software Tool Integration with the Selected Devices

WP3 – HESS Dimensioning, Integration and Verification of Developed Software Tools

T3.2 – Integration of software tools with selected devices

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

API	Application Programming Interface
BESS	Battery Energy Storage System
BMS	Battery Management System
CPU	Central Processing Unit
EMS	Energy Management System
DER	Distributed Energy Resources
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EMS	Energy Management System
EV	Electrical Vehicle
FZJ	Forschungszentrum Jülich (Research Center Jülich)
HESS	Hybrid Energy Storage System
HP	Heat Pump
HyDEMS	Hybrid Distributed Energy Management System
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Internet Protocol
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LPC	Legacy Protocol Converter
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
QoS	Quality of Service
SoC	State of Charge
TES	Thermal Energy Storage
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
XML	eXtensible Markup Language

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The primary objective of the InterSTORE project is to unlock the potential of distributed energy resources and energy storage within energy systems. Achieving this goal requires the monitoring and control of a vast array of distributed assets through advanced energy management systems. By effectively managing these assets, we can harness their flexibility to achieve several key outcomes: decarbonizing the energy system, increasing the share of locally produced energy in overall consumption, enhancing the grid stability, and reducing energy bills for consumers.

Interoperability, the ability of different systems, devices, and applications to communicate and work together seamlessly, are crucial requirements to achieve these goals. Without interoperability, systems cannot exchange information effectively. This would lead to inefficiencies and missed opportunities for optimization. In the context of energy systems, this means that, without a common language, the full potential of distributed energy resources and storage units cannot be realized. To address the interoperability requirement, the InterSTORE project focused efforts in the development of an interoperability software toolkit, particularly within Work Package 2. A crucial component of this toolkit, the legacy protocol converter (LPC), was developed to establish a standardized, secure, scalable, and flexible communication system in energy systems.

Typically, energy assets are equipped with communication systems that enable them to interface with energy management systems (EMSs). These systems utilize various industry standards, such as Modbus, or methods suited for Internet of Things applications, like message queuing telemetry transport (MQTT). The diversity extends beyond communication protocols and messaging formats to include different implementation architectures, such as client-server and publish-subscribe models. When different assets employ varying approaches, a transformation process becomes essential. The LPC supports several transformations, enabling seamless switching from client-server protocols (e.g., Modbus) to publish-subscribe models (e.g., NATS), facilitating multiple end-to-multiple end communication. Additionally, the LPC can generate messages in the standard IEEE 2030.5 format, ensuring a common understanding of structured messages. In essence, this converter allows devices and EMSs to communicate effectively with newer technologies and other legacy systems, maintaining interoperability across diverse communication methods.

The task that led to this report, T3.2, aimed at integrating the LPC in selected devices in project pilots. The report details how and why particular devices (e.g., large scale grid batteries and electrical heat pumps) were selected to showcase the integration in German, Spanish, and Austrian pilots. This report demonstrates a variety of transformations from/to devices, including Modbus-to-NATS and MQTT-to-NATS conversions, as well as mapping from non-standard message formats to *DERStatus* and *MirrorMeteringList* data models of IEEE 2030.5.

Readers are advised to read this report jointly with *D3.3 Report on the Software Tool Integration with Selected Platforms*, as devices and EMSs constitute the overall nexus for monitoring and control of hybrid energy storage systems and thus, represent the end points of communications enabled by the LPC. While specific applications may require different efforts in integration (e.g., different data models and communication workflows), the combination of these two documents provides comprehensive coverage and valuable insights, derived from project pilot activities, that can guide future implementations.

1 Introduction

1.1 Background

In the context of a renewable-driven energy system, energy storage plays a crucial role in balancing supply and demand, and thus enhancing the overall efficiency of the grid. By the end of 2023, Europe's total operating Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS) fleet reached approximately 36 GWh. The residential segment accounted for 63% of this capacity, followed by large-scale battery systems (21%), and commercial & industrial systems (9%) [1]. While the battery storage infrastructure expands, other technologies that can act as controllable electrical loads such as electric vehicles (EVs) and heat pumps (HPs) can also contribute to the storage potential. To address the complexities and challenges of renewable-driven energy systems, a hybridization approach is essential, combining various technologies to optimize performance and achieve seamless energy management. However, each technology comes with its vendor diversity; for example, Stellantis alone offered 16 plug-in-hybrid and 29 full EV models by 2023 [2]. Achieving interoperability, which enables different systems, devices, and applications to communicate and function together seamlessly, is vital for harmonizing different storage units' operations and realizing consolidated energy management goals.

Interoperability has two critical aspects. The first is syntactic interoperability, which ensures that data exchanged between systems are structured in a standardized format. Without syntactic interoperability, systems struggle to interpret and process data correctly, leading to inefficiencies and miscommunication. The InterSTORE project adopts standard data models of IEEE2030.5 [3] to achieve syntactic interoperability. In essence, IEEE2030.5 also serves for semantic interoperability ensuring consistent interpretation of exchanged information by defining mechanisms for exchanging application messages and the security features used to protect the application messages. The second important aspect is the need for a connective technology that supports secure, many-to-many, lightweight, and flexible data exchange over standardized data models. While IEEE2030.5 specifies the data models, it is possible to exchange IEEE2030.5-compatible data over various communication technologies that operate on TCP/IP. This project uses NATS [4] as a connective technology for its scalability, security, hardware-agnosticism.

The interoperability concept pursued in the InterSTORE project, namely exchanging IEEE 2030.5 data over NATS network, implies a significant change from the state-of-the-art in energy systems. At the time of writing this report, communication protocols such as Modbus [5] and MQTT [6] were widely used for connecting energy management systems (EMSs) and distributed energy resources (DERs). Modbus, a master-slave protocol, is prevalent in industrial automation due to its simplicity and reliability. However, its limitations in handling large volumes of data make it less suitable for energy management applications that often require many-to-many communication. Furthermore, Modbus operates by reading and writing to pre-defined registers. This requires additional back-end processes to construct communicated data in IEEE 2030.5 formats. On the other hand, MQTT, a publish-subscribe protocol, is designed for efficient communication in IoT environments. Its ability to handle low bandwidth and unstable networks makes it a good candidate for large-scale integration of DERs. Besides the communication architecture, these protocols have differences how they organize data. In contrast, MQTT is a text-based protocol that allows data to be formatted in customized or standardized ways including IEEE 2030.5.

One of the main technologies delivered by the InterSTORE project is the legacy protocol converter (LPC). This innovative tool plays a crucial role in implementing the InterSTORE interoperability concept by providing easy-to-integrate add-ons to existing systems. The LPC facilitates seamless communication between different connection technologies and data

models, enabling the integration of diverse DERs into a unified energy management infrastructure. By translating and harmonizing data from various protocols, such as Modbus and MQTT, into IEEE2030.5-compatible formats that can be communicated over NATS network, the converter ensures that all components can communicate effectively, thereby enhancing the overall efficiency and reliability of the energy management system.

Before the development of the legacy protocol converter, similar efforts aimed at achieving interoperability in energy systems were undertaken. One notable example is the Open Field Message Bus (OpenFMB) adapter [7], a portable application designed to translate smart grid and industry protocols such as Modbus and DNP3 into IoT protocols like NATS, MQTT, and DDS. The original OpenFMB adapter was subsequently extended to facilitate the exchange of standardized data models, including IEEE 2030.5 and IEC 61850, over message buses such as NATS. Likewise, VILLASnode is a gateway supports several protocols and interfaces, including general-purpose broker-based messaging protocols like Advanced Message Queuing Protocol (AMQP) and MQTT while using standard data models such as IEC 61850 [8]. These advancements laid the groundwork for the LPC, which further enhances interoperability by providing easy-to-integrate add-ons to existing system, with the purpose of supporting several use cases of storage hybridization.

The LPC is a recent tool developed to enhance interoperability in energy systems within the InterSTORE project. To guide future users on how to implement the LPC effectively at the device level, several reference implementations were pursued within the InterSTORE project Task 3.2.

1.2 Objectives of the Report

This report is the outcome of the Task 3.2 of the InterSTORE project. Its ultimate target is to help future users of the LPC, to integrate into their existing systems. The specific goals of this report can be summarized as follows:

1. This report showcases real-world examples of the LPC integration to devices based on the experience gained within the InterSTORE project pilots in Germany and Spain. It presents the target use cases of the LPC in these pilots, maps the communication requirements of use cases to specific deployment scenarios, and documents the process of integrating the LPC into the devices.
2. This report offers practical guidance to the future users of the LPC by presenting a detailed discussions on the lessons learned through the pilot activities.

It is important to note that DER devices and EMS platform constitute the overall nexus for monitoring and control of energy systems. The LPC can be integrated to both sides of this nexus with the purpose of transformation from legacy data models/communication protocols into IEEE 2030.5/ NATS based communication. This report is specifically focused on integration efforts that occur at the DER side (device level). The German, Spanish, and Austrian pilots of the InterSTORE project present concrete instances of the approach, in which software tools are integrated directly with or close to the devices being monitored or controlled. Therefore, this report presents content from the German, Spanish, and Austrian pilots in respective chapters. On the other hand, in the Portuguese and Italian pilots, the integration takes only place at the platform level, where devices are monitored and managed remotely. The documentation of the platform-side integration is covered in *Deliverable D3.3 – Integration to Platform*. In this regard, the current report *D3.2 Report on the Software Tool Integration with Selected Devices* and *D3.3 Report on the Software Tool Integration with Selected Platforms* are complementary documents. The authors advise the readers to view both re-

ports to understand the alternative (at the device side or the platform side) and complementary (e.g. double LPC deployment to enable IEEE 2030.5 communication between non-native end points) implementation approaches.

2 Integration in the German pilot

The Living Lab Energy Campus (LLEC) at Forschungszentrum Jülich (FZJ, “Jülich Research Center”) functions as a testbed for evaluating innovative hardware and software solutions for district energy systems under near-real conditions. This environment, which is scientifically monitored and includes real users, leverages the existing infrastructure of FZJ, one of Europe's largest interdisciplinary research centers. The research center is a self-contained district with minimal infrastructural connections to the surrounding area. Within LLEC, various energy demonstrators for both energy generation and storage are integrated into the existing infrastructure, making it an ideal testbed for future multi-modal district energy systems with a high share of intermittent renewable energies. The Commercial Flexibility Pilot focuses on deploying harmonization software protocols to integrate different distributed storage applications, ensuring interoperability, and exploring synergies of Hybrid Energy Storage Systems (HESS) to enable their operation as conventional Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS) with enhanced performance.

In the pilot conducted in FZJ, the devices to integrate the interoperability software were selected based on their ability to fulfill the requirements set by the two project use cases: grid supporting BESS and multi-physics flexibility optimization. Being the interoperability software tool, the LPC, was the main enabler for these use cases, ensuring seamless integration and communication between different energy assets and energy management systems.

This section serves as a formal report on how the LPC is integrated to the devices in the German pilot. It is organized as follows: Subsection 2.1 briefly introduces the target use cases that the pilot pursues. Subsection 2.2 introduces the assets required for these use cases. Subsection 2.3 defines the communication workflow, specifying (i) the data each device should send to the EMS platform for the targeted use case and (ii) the data the EMS platform should send to the devices. Subsection 2.4 details how a running and functioning instance of the LPC was integrated into these devices. Subsection 2.5 presents a technical discussion elaborating on specific challenges in integration, comments about potential usefulness, and difficulties in future implementations.

2.1 Target Use Cases

As outlined in Task 1.2, the German pilot is dedicated to showcasing two use cases (UCs):

- UC3: Grid supporting BESS
- UC8: Multiphysics flexibility optimization for home management systems and their global integration

The pilot activity to demonstrate grid supportive BESS requires building a hybrid energy storage system within the private power grid of the FZJ campus. In principle, a grid-supportive BESS can address various types of events, each requiring a distinct type of flexibility utilization. For instance, instantaneous frequency deviations can be managed through high power injection or consumption for short durations, while prolonged outages can be mitigated by continuous injection or consumption at lower power rates. Hybridization enhances the grid service capacity, enabling the system to handle a wider range of situations effectively. For these reasons, the demonstrations included both high power and high energy batteries within the FZJ campus.

The image below depicts the targeted UCs within the schematic overview of the setup at FZJ. It highlights the various assets involved in the UCs and EMSs that monitor/control the assets

and shows these assets' native communication methods (Modbus/MQTT). To pursue the InterSTORE interoperability concept, the LPC was integrated to these assets. The next subsections introduce each individual asset in detail and define the required communication flow to fulfill the functional requirements set by the UCs.

Figure 1: Schematic overview of integration setup in FZJ.

It is important to note that Figure 1 presents the targeted LPC integration into devices and platforms in a consolidated way. However, this document details only the integration in the left-hand side of the figure. For the details of the platform side integration, the complementary report *D3.3 Report on the Software Tool Integration with Selected Platforms* must be referred.

2.2 Involved Devices

2.2.1 High-Power Battery

The high-power battery system at FZJ (1.5 MW/0.525 MWh) comprises three Riello SPS HE 500 inverters. Each inverter can be managed using two Modbus-based communication cards: NetMan 204, which retrieves information from the inverter, and Energy Manager EXTENDED, which controls the inverters. To achieve the InterSTORE interoperability concept, an LPC instance with Modbus-to-NATS and NATS-to-Modbus transformations can be implemented. Given the high-power nature of the battery, its state information can change rapidly during operation. Therefore, for grid services requiring quick adjustments in output power (e.g., dynamic frequency containment), a sufficiently frequent reading interval must be established.

2.2.2 High-Energy Battery

The high-energy battery system at FZJ (0.5 MW/2.5 MWh) consists of a single Tesla Megapack unit. The entire system can be monitored and controlled through Modbus-based communication with the Tesla Site controller. Similar to the high-power battery, the reading frequency of the LPC (for Modbus-to-NATS transformation) must be determined by the temporal requirements of the use case.

2.2.3 Photovoltaic Generator

The large PV field (1.1 MWp) installed at FZJ consists of two subsystems, monitored and controlled by two SMA Data Manager devices. The PV modules are divided into eight groups, each managed by a dedicated Sunny Tripower CORE2 inverter from SMA Solar Technology. Each inverter provides a substantial maximum AC output power of 110 kW, ensuring reliable and efficient energy conversion for large-scale installations. With a wide DC input voltage range from 200 V to 1,000 V, the inverter supports versatile PV module configurations, offering flexibility in system design. Operating at a peak efficiency of 98.6%, it minimizes energy

losses and maximizes overall system performance. Communication with the system is based on a specific implementation of the Modbus protocol, known as SunSpec Modbus. Similar to high-power and high-energy batteries Modbus-NATS transformations can be enabled through the use of LPC.

2.2.4 Heat Pumps

At FZJ, the waste heat generated by the supercomputer is utilized in a low-temperature district heating network to provide heating for seven buildings. The heat pumps connected to this network, along with the thermal energy storage units in the buildings, implement air-to-water heat transfer. One of these heat pumps, a Vitocal 350-HT Pro model manufactured by Viessmann, was integrated into the energy management system to demonstrate Use Case 8 with the help of the LPC. The default communication protocol for this heat pump is BACnet, which does not support Modbus. However, FZJ's technical department has installed a local controller that communicates directly via BACnet and passes external control set points if deemed safe. Therefore, users who wish to monitor and control the heat pump must interface with an MQTT adapter. This approach was followed during the demonstration phase, showcasing both asset type and communication diversity. Consequently, the LPC interfacing the heat pump with the EMS was used to read/write from/to the MQTT topics of the heat pump and its thermal energy storage (TES).

Relevant data from the heat pump include the supply and return temperatures from the evaporator and condenser, as well as the electrical power consumption of the heat pump itself. For the TES topics, since the system does not provide an estimation of its SoC, the top and bottom temperatures are collected. All this data is gathered and used by the EMS algorithm to estimate the coefficient of performance (COP) of the heat pump and the current state of the TES. With this information, new set points can be defined to optimize the overall system's energy usage.

2.2.5 Power Quality Meters

The information provided by PQ meters is crucial for the energy management algorithms in both use cases, as it enables a comprehensive understanding of the overall network behavior. The devices in use are the PQI-DA smart meters from the company A-eberle. These meters comply with major PQ standards (i.e., the 61000 series) and offer a wide range of data. However, not all available information is necessary for the demonstrations in the German pilot. Therefore, only the following relevant data will be collected: network frequency, line-to-neutral voltages, line currents, and line powers (active, reactive, and apparent). Communication with these devices is based on Modbus TCP, with all registers formatted as "float 32".

2.3 Targeted Communication Workflow

For UC3, the high-power and high-energy BESSs have been integrated into the already developed FIWARE-based ICT platform of the campus. A control algorithm for voltage control on the medium-voltage level has been deployed as an "application" of the platform, thus serving as EMS. The EMS continuously monitors the voltage profile, to verify that it is within a certain threshold with respect to the nominal value. In case of under voltages due to an increase of the load on a node, the closest BESS is forced to compensate for the voltage drop by injecting power into the system. If the intervention of the first battery is not sufficient, the second closest battery is called up to compensate. Even if current regulations impose that the voltage drop must be compensated within 15 minutes, the EMS is developed to compensate it in 5 minutes. Further adjustments are possible if needed. As soon as the load on the node decreases, and the need to compensate for voltage drops is not present, the BESSs

injections are slowly decreased. Finally, when possible, the BESSs are re-charged to full capacity.

In this framework, the communication system including the LPC was designed in a way to transfer the following data between devices on the field and the EMS in 1-second intervals:

- 1- From devices to EMS: (i) node voltages from the PQ meters, (ii) active power consumption of the electrical loads, (iii) SoC of the BESSs, (iv) active power injections/consumptions of the BESSs
- 2- From EMS to devices: (i) control set points to the BESSs.

For UC8, the multi-physics energy management concept developed in work package 4 set the communication requirements. The interested readers are advised to visit the *Deliverable 4.1 New generation EMS for HEMS, HESS and flexibility management report* to access formal presentation of the pursued energy management concept. This document sets dynamic adaptability as an important quality criterion. If the energy management cannot adapt to fluctuating levels of renewable energy generation, it may miss opportunities to capitalize on periods of high renewable availability. Considering that the PV output can change very quickly with the moving clouds, the communication system must be established such that it enables frequent updates of set points to the controllable flexible devices such as high-power battery and heat pump. Therefore, the communication system including the LPC was designed in a way to transfer the following data between devices and EMS in 1-minute intervals:

- 1- From devices to EMS: (i) SoC of the BESS, (ii) SoC of the TES connected to the HP, (iii) active power consumption of the electrical loads, (iv) active power injection of the PV
- 2- From EMS to devices (after execution of EMS algorithm): (i) control set points to the BESS, (ii) control set points to the HP.

2.4 Software Integration

2.4.1 Integration Medium

For the LPC to connect the FZJ devices to the InterSTORE interoperability layer, a Raspberry Pi (RPI) model 4b with 8 GB of RAM was used. This low-cost yet powerful microcomputer offers the versatility and processing power needed to efficiently handle LPC. Its compact size and energy efficiency make it ideal for integration into larger, diverse frameworks without significantly increasing costs. Additionally, its extensive support for customization and connectivity ensures seamless integration within various infrastructure setups. The RPI's Linux-based operating system is an excellent choice for deploying the LPC, providing stability, flexibility, and access to a wide range of open-source tools that simplify customization and development. Its native support for Docker further enhances its appeal by enabling containerization, streamlining deployment, and ensuring consistent performance across different environments. These features collectively enable efficient and scalable solutions within the German pilot's infrastructure. Due to its flexibility, the NATS server, a key component of the InterSTORE-based IEEE2030.5 communication, was also deployed on the RPI using Docker containers.

2.4.2 Integration Steps

This part aims to guide the readers in future uses of the LPC by presenting the pilot activities in German pilot as a reference. Therefore, the following documentation lists the integration steps in a form that is abstracted from the specifics of the pilot. Nevertheless, the information provided in parenthesis reveals how the abstracted steps are implemented in German pilot.

For instance, Step 1 should be read as follows: *A NATS server should be deployed in the integration medium. This can essentially be a local controller of a device or a cloud server. In the German pilot of the InterSTORE project, a NATS server was deployed as a Docker container on the RPi.* Likewise, since the message mappings are specific to the transformations, these details are presented in Table 1 rather than the following abstract list.

- 1 Deploy a NATS server (Docker container created from *nats:latest* image) on the integration medium (RPi).
- 2 Deploy an MQTT broker (Mosquitto MQTT broker) on the integration medium (RPi or dedicated server, like FIWARE MQTT broker).
- 3 Configure Modbus servers of devices (PV, PQ meters, and BESS) to allow the LPC to read status data (respectively power injection, node voltages, power consumption, and SoC) from the corresponding registers in the pre-defined interval (for UC3 1 second and for UC8 15 seconds).
- 4 Configure MQTT agents of the devices communicating over MQTT (heat pump) to publish status data (lower and upper temperature of the TES) in certain intervals (1-minute).
- 5 Ensure the presence of a network connecting NATS server to MQTT broker and Modbus devices.
- 6 Configure legacy protocol converter:
For messages to be sent to the EMS:
 - 6.1 Assign corresponding incoming connection (MQTT or Modbus depending on the connected device).
 - 6.2 Choose the NATS server as outgoing connection.
 - 6.3 Choose file format for each message to be published (JSON).
 - 6.4 Choose IEEE2030.5 data model for outgoing connection (MirrorMeteringList for the HP and DERStatus for the BESS).
 - 6.5 Map the incoming message to the IEEE2030.5 message format selected in Step 6.4.For messages to be received from the EMS:
 - 6.6 Choose NATS server as the incoming connection.
 - 6.7 Assign corresponding outgoing connection (MQTT or Modbus depending on the connected device).
 - 6.8 Choose the file format if the outgoing connection is MQTT (XML).
 - 6.9 Map the incoming IEEE2030.5 to the required outgoing message format (specific message type consumed by the MQTT agent of the HP) or Modbus write registers.
- 7 Deploy the legacy protocol converter.

2.4.3 LPC Transformations

During the pilot activities, a variety of transformation was implemented in the LPC and demonstrated. The detailed presentation of all transformations would not serve the core goal

of this report. Therefore, only the transformations required to implement bidirectional communication for UC8 are detailed in Table 1.

Table 1: List of transformations performed by the LPC in German pilot devices.

Description	From	To
Read HP measurements	Connection: MQTT-HESS Topic: der/hp/status IEEE2030.5 model: --	Connection: NATS-Server Topic: nats/hp/status IEEE2030.5 model: mirrorMeterReadingList
Read battery measurements	Connection: ModbusTCP-battery1 Modbus Request: -modbus-function-code:3 IEEE2030.5 model: --	Connection: NATS-Server Topic: nats/bat/status IEEE2030.5 model: DERStatus
Read PV measurements	Connection: PV-inv1 Modbus Request: -modbus-function-code:3	Connection: NATS-Server Topic: nats/pv/status IEEE2030.5 model: mirrorMeterReadingList
Read load measurements	Connection: Riello-PQI Modbus Request: -modbus-function-code:3	Connection: NATS-Server Topic: nats/load/status IEEE2030.5 model: mirrorMeterReadingList
Assign set-points to HP	Connection: NATS-Server Topic: nats/setpoints/heatpump IEEE2030.5 model: derControl	Connection: MQTT-HESS Topic: der/hp/setpoint IEEE2030.5 model: --
Assign set-points to battery	Connection: NATS-Server Topic: nats/setpoints/battery IEEE2030.5 model: derControl	Connection: ModbusTCP-battery1 Topic: -- IEEE2030.5 model: --

The following paragraphs summarize the important elements of the defining these transformations in the LPC configuration.

First, as shown in [Figure 2](#), the input/output connections of the LPC are defined. The presented section of the configuration file indicates the LPC's capability to transform between NATS-Server, MQTT-HESS, ModbusTCP-battery1. The connections to PQ meter (Riello-PQI in Table 1) and PV (PV-inv1 in Table 1) are not shown as they follow the same structure as the battery end point. The IP host and port numbers of the pilot are censored for the sake of security.

```
connections:
- name: NATS-Server
  type: NATS
  host: [REDACTED]
  port: [REDACTED]
  reconnect: true
- name: MQTT-HESS
  type: MQTT
  version: 3
  host: [REDACTED]
  port: [REDACTED]
- name: ModbusTCP-battery1
  type: Modbus
  host: [REDACTED]
  port: [REDACTED]
```

Figure 2: German pilot LPC configuration - connections.

The second important step of the LPC configuration is to define all required transformations. Figure 3 presents the details of one of the transformations implemented in the German pilot. “connection” section shows that this transformation is from ModbusTCP-battery1 to NATS-Server. In this example, the transformation is programmed to read the battery status in 15 seconds intervals. Upon the reading, it creates a JSON message, formatted according to IEEE2030.5 data model *DERStatus*, and publishes this message in the NATS network over the local NATS-Server (practically a Docker container of a NATS server instance). In this process, the SoC value read from the Modbus register 51 is mapped to *DER-Status.stateOfChargeStatus.value* element in the JSON message.

```

- name: Bat publishes status
description: LPC reads the TCPModbus registers and creates a JSON message
validate-ieee2030-5: true
connections:
  incoming-connection:
    - ModbusTCP-battery1
  outgoing-connection:
    - NATS-Server
  outgoing-topic: nats/bat/status
  outgoing-format: JSON
to-outgoing:
  to-topic: nats/bat/status
  message: |-
    {
      "DERStatus": {
        "readingTime": $timestamp,
        "stateOfChargeStatus": {
          "dateTime": $timestamp,
          "value": {
            "value": {
              "lpc:mapping": {
                "path": "51",
                "type": "integer"
              }
            }
          }
        }
      }
    }
interval-request:
  interval: 15000
  request:
    modbus-function-code: 3
    modbus-device-id: 1
    modbus-registers:
      - register-address: 51
      type: int16

```

Figure 3: LPC configurations in German pilot - an example transformation.

2.4.4 Demonstration

This section presents some of the results that showcases the integration of the LPC with the selected devices in the German pilot. As the scope of this document is limited to the interoperability tool, the demonstrations focus on the validation of the IEEE2030.5 compatibility of the messages produced by the LPC and their transportation on the NATS network. Three screenshots below provide instances of the messages generated by the LPC in German pilot at different trials.

The first screenshot, depicted in [Figure 4](#), illustrates the structure and content of the message constructed upon reading the characteristics of the Riello battery, highlighting key elements of IEEE2030.5 data model such as *DERCapability*.

```

2025-04-11 11:51:35,167 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.modbus.AbstractModbusRequestHandler -- Frame sent: 00000000006010303640002 {}
2025-04-11 11:51:35,167 INFO -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.TransformationHandler -- Transformed message: {
  "der": {
    "description": "BESS",
    "dERCapability": {
      "DERType": {
        "value": 80
      },
      "modesSupported": {
        "dERControlType": {
          "value": [
            0,
            1
          ]
        }
      },
      "rtgMaxW": {
        "value": 595000,
        "powerOfTenMultiplier": {
          "value": 0
        }
      },
      "uom": {
        "value": 38
      }
    },
    "rtgMaxWh": {
      "value": 2616000,
      "powerOfTenMultiplier": {
        "value": 0
      },
      "uom": {
        "value": 72
      }
    },
    "rtgMaxChargeRateW": {
      "value": 595000,
      "powerOfTenMultiplier": {
        "value": 0
      },
      "uom": {
        "value": 38
      }
    },
    "rtgMaxDischargeRateW": {
      "value": 595000,
      "powerOfTenMultiplier": {
        "value": 0
      },
      "uom": {
        "value": 38
      }
    }
  }
}

```

Figure 4: Reading DER capability of Riello battery through LPC.

The second screenshot, depicted in [Figure 5](#), shows how the Modbus registers holding the SoC data of the Riello battery is read by the LPC. Furthermore, it presents the message constructed upon reading the status. This screenshot shows that the SoC value (100%) was mapped to DERStatus.value in JSON message created by the LPC.

```

2025-03-04 14:59:43,391 INFO -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.TransformationHandler -- Publishing Modbus interval request {}
2025-03-04 14:59:43,393 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.TransformationHandler -- Building Modbus requests... {}
2025-03-04 14:59:43,435 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.ModbusHandler -- Starting register address: 51 {}
2025-03-04 14:59:43,436 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.ModbusHandler -- Quantity: 1 {}
2025-03-04 14:59:43,437 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.ModbusHandler -- Function code: READ_HOLDING_REGISTERS value: 3 {}
2025-03-04 14:59:43,460 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.modbus.AbstractModbusRequestHandler -- Sending Modbus request to device: 1 {}
2025-03-04 14:59:43,500 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.ModbusHandler -- Bytes: [0, 100] {}
2025-03-04 14:59:43,514 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.ModbusHandler -- Registers: [100] {}
2025-03-04 14:59:43,656 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.ObjectTransformer -- path: 51, value: 100 {}
2025-03-04 14:59:43,818 INFO -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.TransformationHandler -- Transformed message: {
  "DERStatus": {
    "readingTime": 1741096783522,
    "stateOfChangeStatus": {
      "dateTime": 1741096783522,
      "value": {
        "value": 100
      }
    }
  }
}
2025-03-04 14:59:43,818 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.TransformationHandler -- Publishing message to topic: nats/bat/status with message: {
  "DERStatus": {
    "readingTime": 1741096783522,
    "stateOfChangeStatus": {
      "dateTime": 1741096783522,
      "value": {
        "value": 100
      }
    }
  }
}
}

```

Figure 5: Reading DER status of Riello battery through LPC.

The third screenshot (Figure 6) shows the logging of messages generated by the LPC upon initialization. These logs are created by leveraging the validation function of the LPC. The validation process runs at the configuration stage and checks whether the transformations defined in LPC configuration files (e.g. in Figure 2) adhere to the required message format. The logging outputs show that all the transformations pass these tests in German pilot.

```

2025-03-04 14:47:24,228 INFO -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.configuration.Configuration -- Reading configuration: config_lpc_der.yml {}
2025-03-04 14:47:24,593 INFO -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.configuration.Configuration -- Validating messages for transformation: HP publishes status {}
2025-03-04 14:47:24,737 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.ObjectTransformer -- Transformation validated successfully {}
2025-03-04 14:47:24,738 INFO -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.configuration.Configuration -- Validating messages for transformation: Bat publishes status {}
2025-03-04 14:47:24,748 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.ObjectTransformer -- Transformation validated successfully {}
2025-03-04 14:47:24,749 INFO -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.configuration.Configuration -- Validating messages for transformation: LPC sends set points to HP agent {}
2025-03-04 14:47:24,762 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.ObjectTransformer -- Transformation validated successfully {}
2025-03-04 14:47:24,764 INFO -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.configuration.Configuration -- Validating messages for transformation: LPC sends set points to Bat agent {}
2025-03-04 14:47:24,775 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.ObjectTransformer -- Transformation validated successfully {}
2025-03-04 14:47:24,776 INFO -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.configuration.Configuration -- Validating messages for transformation: Meter publishes status {}
2025-03-04 14:47:24,790 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.ObjectTransformer -- Transformation validated successfully {}

```

Figure 6: LPC validations on IEEE2030.5 in German pilot.

2.5 Lessons Learned

The integration of the LPC into selected energy assets within the German pilot has provided valuable insights into the practical challenges and opportunities associated with achieving interoperability in complex energy systems. This sub-chapter aims to summarize the key lessons learned from this integration process, highlighting both the technical and operational aspects that influenced the outcomes. By reflecting on these experiences, we can identify best practices, potential pitfalls, and areas for improvement that will inform future implementations and contribute to the broader goals of the InterSTORE project.

2.5.1 Temporal Synchronization Challenges

One of the key lessons learnt from the integration process is the difficulty of achieving temporal synchronization between different time references. In the German pilot, some devices accessed the InterSTORE interoperability layer via an LPC-triggered process, while others through an endpoint-driven process. Specifically, the status data of the Riello battery and PQ meter are read from their Modbus registers, with the reading frequency and instants determined by the LPC configuration. These reading events were initiated by the LPC. Conversely, the status data of the HPs is sent to the LPC by the MQTT agent of the HP, with the event initiated by the endpoint connected to the LPC. During the experiments, the LPC lacked inherent logic to synchronize the timing of reading from a Modbus register with the timing of publishing by an MQTT agent. This lack of synchronization can pose a problem when time synchronization is crucial for the accuracy of control decisions taken by the EMS such as assigning new set points to the controllable DERs. It is important to note that this problem naturally arises when data published by MQTT endpoints and data obtained by reading Modbus registers must be consolidated in a single process. Therefore, addressing this synchronization issue was identified as an action point to enhance LPC's applicability in such challenging scenarios.

Despite the challenges of temporal synchronization, another crucial element of the InterSTORE interoperability concept—the use of IEEE2030.5 data models—offers a simplified solution. These data models include time-stamped status data in relevant message types (*MirrorMeteringList* and *DERStatus*), allowing the EMS to analyze timing mismatches and implement custom logic to align the data to a unified time reference. In the German pilot, particularly in UC8, this alignment was achieved by integrating a simple Python program on the EMS platform side. This program, indicated as Synchronization Container in Figure 7, serves as a logic gateway into the EMS platform, SMP 4250 [9]. As the control algorithm runs in 1-minute intervals to determine the set points for the next minute, the Python program applies "if clauses" to ensure all endpoints' status data (PV, PQ meter, battery, HP) are accounted for within the given minute. By utilizing the time stamps injected into the messages through the IEEE2030.5 mappings of the LPC, the program ensures that only complete and synchronized

data is posted to the EMS platform over the RestAPI and then used by the EMS algorithm to determine the set points.

Figure 7: Integration of synchronization module into Eaton SMP in the German Pilot

2.5.2 Challenges with IEEE2030.5 Data Model Choice

Another lesson learnt from the German pilot is the challenge posed by the abstracted definitions within the IEEE2030.5 data models. As the device landscape diversifies with the inclusion of multi-energy devices such as heat pumps or storage elements leveraging other energy carriers like thermal energy storage, certain data structures, such as *DER-Status.stateOfChargeStatus.value.value* become impracticable for representing relevant data. In these cases, developers can exploit more loosely defined data models, such as *MirrorMeteringList*, as done in the German pilot. For instance, to report the upper and lower temperatures of the TES, the German pilot utilized dedicated *MirrorMeterReadingList.mirrorMetering* items. However, interpreting such message formats requires system developers to implement custom logic on the EMS side, which limits the convenience and straightforward use of IEEE2030.5 data models.

3 Integration in the Spanish Pilot

The Advanced Grid Lab (AGL), located in Valencia, serves as a cutting-edge experimental platform dedicated to the development, testing, and validation of next-generation power system technologies. Designed and operated by HESStec, one of the pioneering companies in hybrid energy storage systems, the lab is a cornerstone of innovation in grid modernization and energy transition strategies.

GridLab is distinguished by its unique capacity and flexibility to emulate real-world grid events and scenarios, providing a controlled, yet highly flexible environment to study a variety of grid phenomena. This enables researchers and developers to simulate faults, demand variations, source intermittency, and complex system dynamics that typically occur in modern, renewable-rich power systems. Such versatility is crucial for evaluating the robustness and effectiveness of new energy technologies under realistic and challenging conditions.

The lab is equipped with 1.5 MW of connected power, facilitating large-scale experimental validation. One of its core assets is the hybrid storage system, composed of a 250 kW / 250 kWh lithium-ion battery and a 300 kW / 60-second (18 MJ) ultracapacitor bank. This hybrid configuration enables simultaneous long-duration energy support and fast-response power services, critical for mimicking dynamic system needs and for testing grid-forming capabilities under stress conditions.

Additionally, the lab allows for the emulation of renewable energy sources (such as PV or wind) and variable consumption profiles, offering a complete end-to-end testbed for DERs. The facility is particularly focused on Grid Forming (GFM) converter systems, which are vital for enabling stable, inverter-based power systems. These systems are central to HESStec's portfolio and play a pivotal role in the delivery of virtual inertia, power oscillation damping, voltage and frequency control, and other essential grid services.

The AGL provides:

- Hybrid energy storage integration and management via a dedicated InMS (Integrated Management System) platform.
- Real-time system monitoring interfaces and dashboards for observability and control.
- Wide testing capabilities, including testing of novel control algorithms, services under extreme conditions, and interoperability solutions.
- A real-life technology-based space for innovation in power electronics control, grid resilience strategies, and energy system optimization.

The activities described in this section relate specifically to Task 3.2 of the project, involving the deployment and integration of an LPC to enable communication between the lab's grid-forming power inverter device and the used EMS, in compliance with the IEEE 2030.5 standard. This activity is part of the broader effort to validate seamless interoperability between legacy systems and modern protocol-based management solutions within real-time environments like AGL.

3.1 Target Use Cases

The Spanish advanced grid lab is dedicated to showcasing two use cases (UCs) within the project:

- UC4: Innovative Frequency services BESS

- UC7: Adaptive BESS management for autonomous grid operation

The physical scheme of the Lab facility is shown in Figure 8 consist of PSC1 to PSC4, AC/DC converter, and storage elements.

The lab is consisted of two main zones: testing zone and HESS under test (HUT).

1. **Test bench:** Equipment developed by Hesstec with its own highly flexible power electronics, capable of decoupling from the public network to simulate unstable network conditions (low inertia, voltage oscillations, frequency, outages, dips, flicker, etc.), both in generation and in consumption.
2. **HESS Under Test:** Assembled equipment for testing energy storage systems, with hybrid electrochemistry (Lithium FPO Batteries and Ultracapacitors), capable of reacting and stabilizing the test conditions given by the bench

Figure 8: Gridlab Physical Scheme.

3.2 Involved Devices

The integration of the LPC as part of Task 3.2 was carried out using several key assets within the AGL infrastructure. These components form the core of the hybrid energy system platform operated by HESStec. For this specific task, the primary device used for LPC communication and protocol transformation testing was the grid-forming AC/DC converter, which is connected to both energy storage systems and managed via the HyDEMS (Integrated Management System). The subsections below briefly describe the three critical devices involved for Task 3.2.

3.2.1 Grid Forming Converter

The grid-forming converter in the AGL is a high-performance AC/DC power converter capable of operating in grid-forming mode. It provides autonomous voltage and frequency control and is responsible for maintaining grid stability even in weak or islanded grid conditions. Designed to support hybrid energy storage configurations, this converter also allows for real-time bidirectional power exchange with the EMS and other devices in the system. Its advanced control features make it ideal for testing IEEE 2030.5 protocol implementation and system-level services like virtual inertia, black start, and power oscillation damping. It is

worth mentioning that the converter is supported by UCAP and battery pack on its DC side for stable operation.

3.3 Targeted Communication Workflow

This subsection describes the main targeted data exchange between the EMS and the devices involved in Task 3.2 through the integrated LPC. The communication workflow is designed to enable the provision of high-speed, real-time services—such as virtual inertia emulation, fast peak shaving, and other dynamic control applications—by ensuring rapid and reliable data transfer between the EMS and the key components of the hybrid energy system.

3.3.1 Data from Devices to EMS

The device used for this task is AC/DC GFM converter linked to storage element on its own DC link. Each physical asset provides critical real-time measurements to the EMS, which are essential for making decisions regarding system control and operation. For this task, the key information transmitted from the device to the EMS includes:

- **Grid-Forming Converter Device:**
 - **Active Power (P):** Continuously measured and reported to track real-time power delivery.
 - **Reactive Power (Q):** Continuously measured and reported to track real-time power delivery.
 - **Voltage and Frequency Measurements:** Used to evaluate stability and trigger services like frequency support or black start.
 - **Status and Alarms:** Inform the EMS about converter availability and any fault conditions.

3.3.2 Data from EMS to Devices

The EMS, upon processing the collected data and applying its control algorithms, sends control commands (setpoints) to the device to manage the hybrid system's response. The key setpoints communicated include:

- **To the Grid-Forming Converter device:**
 - **Active and reactive Power Setpoints:** Directs the converter on how much active power or reactive to output, aligned with system service requirements.
 - **Mode Control Signals:** Commands to change operating modes (e.g., from grid-following to grid-forming or islanding mode).

3.3.3 Communication Frequency and Timeliness

Due to the high-speed nature of the target services in use case 4 and 7, data exchange must occur at very short intervals to ensure system responsiveness and stability:

- SoC and active power data from the battery and UCAP should be updated every 10–100 milliseconds.
- Setpoints from the EMS to the devices should also be issued in near-real time, with a target latency of less than 200 ms.
- Polling rates for Modbus queries through the LPC have been configured and optimized based on earlier tests to maintain this timing.

This high-frequency communication ensures that the EMS maintains accurate system awareness and can respond almost instantaneously to changing grid conditions.

3.4 Software Integration

This section outlines the deployment and integration process of the LPC, which enables communication over IEEE 2030.5 standard within the InteSTORE project. The activities described for Task 3.2, focusing on LPC integration at the device level, where the device in question is a grid-forming converter located in our advanced grid laboratory. The goal of this deployment is to ensure seamless communication between different components of the system while adhering to standardized protocols for improved interoperability and system efficiency. It should be noted that the deployment of the LPC has been checked and compared with our previous traditional approach using Modbus and CAN-based communication of the device.

As shown in Figure 9, to bridge communication between the power converter and EMS, a virtual machine hosting different Docker containers has been deployed within the device's local network. These containers mainly include:

- **LPC Docker:** Responsible for protocol translation from Modbus to IEEE 2030.5 and vice versa. This translation is essential to facilitate seamless communication between legacy devices and modern energy management systems.
- **Local NATS Docker:** Functions as an intermediary message queue server for bidirectional data exchange. This component enhances the reliability of data transfer, allowing messages to be stored temporarily in case of communication delays or failures.

This adaptation ensures that existing grid components can interact efficiently with newer systems while leveraging modern virtualization and containerization technologies to improve deployment and management processes.

Figure 9: LPC integration into devices in Spanish pilot vs conventional integration.

3.4.1 Integration Medium

For the deployment of the LPC in our Spanish pilot, the chosen medium was a **local server** located within the device network of the AGL in Valencia. This server hosted a **virtual machine (VM)**. The **Docker containers** deployed on this VM encapsulate software components required for communication and protocol conversion. The use of Docker eases deployment, isolation, scalability, and reproducibility.

Three main Docker containers were deployed on the VM:

- **LPC (Legacy Protocol Converter)** container, responsible for translating Modbus-based communication to IEEE 2030.5.
- **NATS server** container, acting as the internal message broker between the devices (e.g., grid-forming converter, battery, UCAP) and the LPC.
- **Node-RED** container, included primarily for testing and visualizing data flow during development and integration.

The screenshot shows the Docker Desktop interface with the following data:

Container CPU usage		Container memory usage					
1.92% / 400% (4 CPUs available)		391.22MB / 3.68GB		Show charts			
<input type="text" value="Search"/> ☰ <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Only show running containers							
<input type="checkbox"/>	Name	Image	Status	CPU (%)	Port(s)	Last started	Actions
<input type="checkbox"/>	docker-interstore		Running (3/3)	1.91%		13 seconds ago	■ : ■
<input type="checkbox"/>	natsServer 05f188792c6c	nats:latest	Running	0.06%	4222:4222 Show all ports (3)	27 seconds ago	■ : ■
<input type="checkbox"/>	node-red-1 2b1f5c420372	nodered/node-red:latest	Running	0.09%	1880:1880	13 seconds ago	■ : ■
<input type="checkbox"/>	legacy-protocol 76c53f2e7ce7	interstore/legacy-protocol	Running	1.76%		27 seconds ago	■ : ■

Figure 10: Docker containers deployed in Spanish pilot.

Docker Compose was used to manage these containers efficiently. This tool allows configuration of multiple containers from a single file and their deployment with a simple command (`docker-compose up`). It also supports configuration of volumes, environment variables, and network settings, which made it ideal for our modular integration strategy. It also ensures that system updates and reconfigurations can be performed seamlessly without disrupting the overall operation.

```
version: '3.7'

services:
  natsServer:
    image: nats:latest
    container_name: natsServer
    environment:
      - PATH=/usr/local/sbin:/usr/local/bin:/usr/sbin:/usr/bin:/sbin:/bin:/
    ports:
      - 4222:4222
      - 6222:6222
      - 8222:8222
    restart: "always"
    network_mode: bridge

  legacy-protocol-converter:
    image: interstore/legacy-protocol-converter:latest
    volumes:
      - ./conf:/app/conf
    restart: "always"
    network_mode: bridge

  node-red:
    image: nodered/node-red:latest
    environment:
      - TZ=Europe/Madrid
    volumes:
      - node-red-data:/data
    ports:
      - "1880:1880"
    network_mode: bridge

volumes:
  node-red-data:
```

Figure 11: Docker compose file for starting Docker services in Spanish pilot.

In the proposed approach, the LPC acts as a translator between the proprietary Modbus communication protocol of the power converter device and the IEEE 2030.5 protocol used by EMS. This bidirectional communication ensures that real-time services can be provided efficiently. A single LPC instance is deployed to manage both transformation directions. This implementation enables real-time monitoring and control of power inverters, facilitating optimal grid performance and system responsiveness. Additionally, by using a single instance for bidirectional communication, the system reduces redundancy and enhances operational efficiency.

3.4.2 Integration Steps

The following steps were performed to complete the integration of the LPC into the system:

- 1 **Provision and configure the local VM** with network access to the GFM converter and other devices.
- 2 **Install Docker and Docker Compose** on the VM to orchestrate container deployment.
- 3 **Create Docker Compose file** defining the LPC, NATS, and Node-RED containers with appropriate configuration and volume mounts.
- 4 **Develop LPC configuration files** including Modbus register mappings and IEEE 2030.5 topic definitions.
- 5 **Deploy and run containers** using docker-compose up, verifying successful startup and inter-container communication.
- 6 **Test the Modbus communication** between LPC and each device via NATS topics using Node-RED visualization.
- 7 **Validate transformation and data flow** by publishing and subscribing to test data streams.

8 Fine-tune polling intervals and QoS settings to ensure reliable real-time operation.

This process ensured that both directions of communication—reading data from the device and writing control commands—were fully operational. The bidirectional functionality is essential for dynamic power services such as virtual inertia and fast peak shaving.

It should be noted that, as shown in the steps, to automate the deployment of the containers, a docker compose has been created with three containers. Docker compose is a docker add-on that makes it easy to deploy and configure docker containers from a single file. It also allows you to start them all at once with the docker compose up command.

3.4.3 LPC Mapping

The LPC was configured to transform incoming Modbus data into appropriate IEEE 2030.5-compatible data models. Similarly, setpoints issued by the EMS using MQTT were translated into corresponding Modbus commands.

This structured mapping ensures clarity and traceability of data from device measurement to EMS decision and back to device control.

```
connections:
- name: NATS-connection
  type: NATS
  host: nats://host.docker.internal
  port: 4222
  reconnect: true
- name: Modbus-connection
  type: Modbus
  host: 172.18.0.139
  port: 502
```

Figure 12: Spanish pilot LPC configuration – connections.

```
- name: JSON IEEE2030.5 to TCP Modbus
description: Example showing transformation of messages from JSON to TCPModbus
connections:
  incoming-connection:
  - Modbus-connection
  outgoing-connection:
  - NATS-connection
  outgoing-format: JSON
  outgoing-topic: event/write
to-incoming:
  modbus-function-code: 6
  modbus-device-id: 1
  modbus-registers:
  - register-address: 1459
    type: int16
    path: /DER/DERControlBase/opModTargetW/value
```

Figure 13: LPC transformation from NATS to Modbus in Spanish pilot.

```
- name: TCP Modbus to JSON IEEE2030.5 Event
description: Example showing transformation of messages from TCPModbus to JSON
connections:
  incoming-connection:
    - Modbus-connection
  outgoing-connection:
    - NATS-connection
  outgoing-topic: event/listen
  outgoing-format: JSON
to-outgoing:
  to-topic: event/send
  message: '{
    "DER": {
      "description": "Gridlab Converter",
      "mrid": {
        "value": "1"
      },
      "activePower": {
        "multiplier": {
          "value": "1"
        },
        "value": {
          "lpc:mapping": {
            "path": "1459",
            "type": "int16"
          }
        }
      }
    },
    "lastUpdateTime": "$timestamp"
  }'
interval-request:
  interval: 1000
  request:
    modbus-function-code: 3
    modbus-device-id: 1
    modbus-registers:
      - register-address: 1459
        type: int16
```

Figure 14: LPC transformation from Modbus to NATS transformation in Spanish pilot.

To standardize the communication, two key transformations were implemented:

- **Reading Data from Inverter to EMS:** The active power of the inverter is mapped to the ActivePower field in the DER structure, with the Modbus 1459 field used as the source. This allows the EMS to accurately monitor power generation and consumption in real time.
- **Sending Setpoints from EMS to Inverter:** The power setpoint is written using the op-ModTargetW field within DERControlBase, which is then mapped to the Modbus 1459 address. This ensures that the EMS can send precise control signals to the inverter, optimizing power flow and grid stability.

By adhering to the IEEE 2030.5 standard, the system enhances interoperability, making it easier to integrate with other modern grid management solutions and smart energy applications.

MODBUS TO IEEE 2030.5					
MODBUS SECTION	MODBUS ADDRESS	DESCRIPTION	IEEE 2030.5 SECTION	IEEE 2030.5 ATTRIBUTE	DESCRIPTION
Converter	1459	Active power of Danfos Converter	DER.ActivePower	value	Active Power in Watts
IEEE 2030.5 TO MODBUS					
IEEE 2030.5 SECTION	IEEE 2030.5 ATTRIBUTE	DESCRIPTION	MODBUS SECTION	MODBUS ADDRESS	DESCRIPTION
DER.DERControlBase	opModTargetW	Active Power in Watts	Converter	1459	Active Power setPoint

Figure 15: Transformation update in Spanish pilot device.

3.4.4 Demonstration

As explained, a single LPC is utilized for bidirectional communication between the power converter and EMS, ensuring seamless data transformation and real-time operations. This configuration streamlines communication while maintaining the integrity and reliability of data exchange. The modular architecture of the LPC allows for future scalability, enabling additional functionalities or system enhancements without requiring major overhauls.

The log file screenshot (Figure 16) from the system demonstrates the successful functioning of the LPC module:

```
-- Incoming message from server for modbus: {"DER": {"DERControlBase": {"opModTargetW": {"value":136}}}} {}
2025-03-26 16:39:55 2025-03-26 15:39:55,007 INFO -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.TransformationHandler
-- Publishing Modbus interval request {}
2025-03-26 16:39:55 2025-03-26 15:39:55,040 INFO -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.TransformationHandler
-- Transformed message: {
2025-03-26 16:39:55 "DER": {
2025-03-26 16:39:55 "description": "Gridlab Converter",
2025-03-26 16:39:55 "nrid": {
2025-03-26 16:39:55 "value": "1"
2025-03-26 16:39:55 },
2025-03-26 16:39:55 "activePower": {
2025-03-26 16:39:55 "multiplier": {
2025-03-26 16:39:55 "value": "1"
2025-03-26 16:39:55 },
2025-03-26 16:39:55 "value": 136
2025-03-26 16:39:55 },
2025-03-26 16:39:55 "lastUpdateTime": 1743003595039
2025-03-26 16:39:55 }
2025-03-26 16:39:55 } {}
2025-03-26 16:39:55 2025-03-26 15:39:55,042 INFO -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.TransformationHandler
-- Incoming message from server for modbus: {"DER": {"DERControlBase": {"opModTargetW": {"value":136}}}} {}
```

Figure 16: Logfile example of the deployment in Spanish pilot.

This log confirms that the LPC is functioning as intended. It reads the power setpoints of the converter in real time and publishes it to the NATS message bus using the *DER.ActivePower* data model. Simultaneously, it receives control setpoints from the EMS by *opModTargetW* and transmits them to the device writing to the correct Modbus address.

As shown in Figure 17 in the green square, it is possible to check that the validation is successful. In the transformation in the opposite direction, it has been disabled, since the output is to Modbus and the IEEE2030.5 model cannot be validated.

```

si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.configuration.Configuration -- Reading configuration: config.yml {}
si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.configuration.Configuration -- Validating messages for transformation: TCP Modbus to JSON IIEE2030.5 Event
- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.ObjectTransformer -- Transformation validated successfully {}
si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.configuration.Configuration -- Validating messages for transformation: JSON IIEE2030.5 to TCP Modbus {}
si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.logging.LoggingInit -- Logging initialized application-wide {}
- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.connections.Connections -- Found 2 connections {}
si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.TransformationHandler -- Transformation: TCP Modbus to JSON IIEE2030.5 Event {}
si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.TransformationHandler -- Transformation: JSON IIEE2030.5 to TCP Modbus {}
- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.TransformationHandler -- Subscribing to incoming topic for Modbus: event/write {}
si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.TransformationHandler -- Publishing Modbus interval request {}
- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.TransformationHandler -- Building Modbus requests... {}
- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.ModbusHandler -- Starting register address: 1532 {}
- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.ModbusHandler -- Quantity: 1 {}
- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.ModbusHandler -- Function code: READ_HOLDING_REGISTERS value: 3 {}
- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.ModbusHandler -- Bytes: [0, 100] {}
- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.ModbusHandler -- Registers: [100] {}
- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.ObjectTransformer -- path: 1532, value: 100 {}
    
```

Figure 17: Logfile validated example of the deployment in Spanish pilot.

This behavior aligns directly with the objectives of Task 3.2 where fast bidirectional communication is essential for implementing fast grid services. The demonstration confirms that our integration supports fast response dynamics necessary for scenarios like virtual inertia emulation and high-speed setpoint delivery.

3.4.5 Performance Evaluation: Speed Test Results

A series of speed tests were conducted to measure the performance of the LPC in varying conditions, analyzing:

- **Polling Rate:** Frequency of Modbus variable queries. Higher polling rates ensure timely data acquisition but can also increase computational load.
- **Data Points:** Number of variables being read. Analyzing multiple variables simultaneously improves system monitoring but may affect latency.
- **CPU Usage:** *text added in yellow. Please remove highlights of yellow for the final version.* mpact on the server running the LPC. Understanding CPU resource consumption helps optimize system performance and ensures that the hardware operates efficiently. For the show case at this step of the project the CPU data are 11th Gen Intel(R) Core(TM) i3-1115G4 @ 3.00GHz.
- **Total Delay:** Time taken for data reception and processing. Reducing delays is crucial for real-time power control and ensuring responsive grid services.

These tests are crucial for evaluating the responsiveness of the system, especially for fast power services that require minimal latency. The results provide insights into how the system behaves under different workloads and configurations, enabling further optimizations where necessary.

With these tests, it can be concluded that the polling rate and the number of data read, influences the performance of the server. To test with fast services, the polling rate was reduced to the minimum possible (around 100 to 150 ms) to avoid triggering a communications error.

Table 2: List of transformation performed by the LPC in Spanish Pilot

Polling rate	Data point	CPU server usage	EMS read difference	Total time
50MS	1	15%	UNSTABLE RECEPTION TIME (5MS)	55MS
100MS	1	15%	UNSTABLE RECEPTION TIME (2MS)	102MS
100MS	10	4%	COMMUNICATION ERROR	-
200MS	10	4%	UNSTABLE RECEPTION TIME (50MS)	250MS

300MS	10	4%	UNSTABLE RECEPTION TIME (50MS)	350MS
300MS	16	4%	UNSTABLE RECEPTION TIME (>100MS)	>400MS
400MS	16	4%	UNSTABLE RECEPTION TIME (>100MS)	>500MS
500MS	16	4%	UNSTABLE RECEPTION TIME (>100MS)	>600MS
800MS	16	4%	UNSTABLE RECEPTION TIME (10MS)	810MS

3.5 Lessons Learned

During the software integration process, we encountered several challenges that required iteration and troubleshooting:

- Initially, the communication would be set up in a unidirectional manner (EMS to device only), which limited visibility into device behavior. We revised the design to enable **bidirectional data exchange** using the LPC and NATS, creating a closed-loop system.
- Determining the optimal polling interval for Modbus registers was non-trivial. High-frequency polling introduced delays and CPU load, while lower frequencies degraded system responsiveness. We conducted timing benchmarks to identify an effective **trade-off between latency and performance**, settling on a 100 ms polling interval for critical services.

It is worth mentioning that the biggest challenge to implement the bidirectional close loop in communications using LPC, was to understand how the LPC transformations worked. Once understood, they were implemented in the configuration file and a bug was discovered in LPC, in the NATS-Modbus transformation, which had to be fixed by the LPC development team and upgraded to the new version to reach the bidirectional communication.

These lessons will guide future LPC integration in other pilots or lab testbeds and serve to reduce configuration effort and deployment time.

Additionally, our test results included performance evaluation metrics such as total communication delay, polling rate impact, and server CPU usage. These are critical insights for scaling the solution to other advanced labs or production deployments where system reliability and timing precision are paramount.

4 Integration in the Austrian pilot

The Renewable Energy Community (REC) Dietach, located in the Upper Austria region, is an administrative organization comprising almost 300 members in close proximity to the village of Dietach. The REC aggregates 175 PV systems with a combined peak power of 2846 kW and has a yearly overall consumption of 3 million kWh. Most members live in one family house with a restaurant, a cinema, and a water pump station, representing the largest consumers. The primary benefit of the members is price stability, cheaper energy prices (for consumers) and higher revenues (for producers), which is based on internal energy allocation done as an administrative step by DSO.

The Austrian Residential Pilot builds upon the current status by enabling real-life monitoring of produced (and stored) energy and aggregating (willing) REC members into a pool, which on one hand optimizes produced energy and on the other offers the remaining energy on the DSO balancing market. Thus, it creates a new revenue stream for REC and a more stable environment for the DSO.

From the 300 members of REC, 20 members participated in InterSTORE project. At these members' houses, a hardware device was installed, which enables communication between PV and batteries at the location to CyberNoc via IEEE2030.5 protocol.

The next sections present a report on how the LPC is integrated into the devices in the Austrian residential pilot. It is organized as follows: Subsection 4.1 briefly introduces the target use cases that the pilot pursues, and the devices involved in these use cases. Subsection 4.2 defines the communication workflow, specifying (i) the data each device should send to the CyberNoc for the targeted use case and (ii) the data the CyberNoc should send to the devices. Subsection 4.3. presents installation procedures, hardware used, and protocol mapping. Subsection 4.4 presents key findings from the done work.

4.1 Target Use Cases

The Austrian pilot targets connecting the energy community, optimally managing it, and showing the benefits of its market participation. More particularly residential pilot covers two use cases (UCs):

- UC1 – DES Flexibility Market Monetisation
- UC2 – Energy community DES utilization

The pilot focuses on showing the ease of implementation of the newly improved protocol IEEE2030.5 over NATS in a real-life environment. Furthermore, the activities in the pilot feature robustness in the face of various network configurations, PV and battery installations, and different versions of inverter software. All the while providing value for members with visualizations of their real-life data and optimization algorithms.

Such ambitious goals can be achieved only with a device-agnostic installation plan. Full Communication Chain (FCC), shown on [Figure 18](#), was devised by CyberGrid with this in mind.

Figure 18: Full Communication Chain deployment in the Austrian pilot.

It is important to note that this document does not explain the entire FCC but only the section on the implementation of LPC into IoTmaxx and its subsequent placement in the household, as shown on Figure 19. More on the FCC can be found in *D5.2 - Report on Software Tools Integration and Test Execution Across the Pilot Sites*.

Figure 19: Architectural presentation of setup in a common household with PV and BESS.

The architectural presentation on Figure 19 shows the common setup in a household with PV and BESS, which are controlled by different inverters. CyberGrid installs the IoTmaxx (hardware hosting LPC in a Docker container) and connects it to the local network via Wi-Fi. Through the internal network, IoTmaxx communicates with the inverter(s). After the connection is established, LPC translates the messages from Modbus into IEEE2030.5 over NATS to CyberGrid EMS solution - CyberNoc, which is managing the REC.

4.1.1 List of inverters

As mentioned already Austrian pilot has a diverse set of PV and BESS devices to be controlled. Table 3 presents an overview on their inverters. The biggest percentage of devices are controlled by Fronius-made inverters (around 50 %), from which Symo 10 is the most

common (around 20 %). The list also includes Huawei, BYD, SolarEdge, and Solax inverters. More about inverters present in the Austrian pilot can be found in *D5.2 - Report on Software Tools Integration and Test Execution Across the Pilot Sites*.

Table 3: Type of inverters in the Austrian pilot.

Manufacturer	Type	Asset type
Fronius	Symo 10, Symo 8.2	PV
Fronius	Symo Gen24 Plus	PV
Fronius	SymoHybrid 5.0	BESS
Huawei	SUN2000, Solar Inverter	PV
SolarEdge	SE9K	PV
Solax	X3-HYBRID-15.0-D G4.2	PV
Huawei	LUNA2000	BESS
Varta	Pulse neo	BESS
BYD	HVM	BESS

4.2 Targeted Communication Workflow

The communication workflow, established in the Austrian pilot, is closely connected to the use cases pursued and the systems set up for their achievement. In UC1, real-time information on active power and availability of the devices was needed to aggregate their available energy and offer it on energy markets. In UC2, we target greater utilization of batteries through their optimal charging. More on use cases and optimizations pursued in the Austrian pilot you can read in *D4.1 - New generation EMS for HEMS, HESS, and flexibility management report*.

In summary, the communication system, including the LPC, was designed in a way to transfer the following data between devices on the field and the CyberNoc in 10-second intervals:

- 1- From devices to CyberNoc: (i) active power, (ii) SoC of the BESSs, (iv) availability of the device
- 2- From CyberNoc to devices: (i) control set points to the BESSs.

4.3 Software Integration

In this section, we briefly explain the approaches to integrate the LPC into the IoTmaxx device, followed by protocol mapping.

4.3.1 Integration Medium

LPC translates data received from REC devices to the InterSTORE novel protocol IEEE2030.5. In this process, IoTmaxx operates as a hardware component and a placeholder for a Docker container. The full name of the HW device used is Maxx GW4100 Gateway LTE 4G (IoTmaxx, n.d.) and is a product of the IoTmaxx company. More details can be found in *D5.2 - Report on Software Tools Integration and Test Execution Across the Pilot Sites***Error! Reference source not found..**

4.3.2 Integration Steps

This section presents the steps taken by the CyberGrid technical team and a dedicated electrician installer at the location in order to connect 20 different devices from the Austrian pilot:

1 Prepare IoTmaxx:

- 1.1 Update its own software.
- 1.2 Docker image installation (of LPC).
- 1.3 LPC mapping - For LPC to start working, it needs to have a YAML file with specifications about the targeted use case, installed in IoTmaxx. YAML files will differ vastly among different use cases, which means that once configured, they can be used for a specific use case only.

Prepare APN

Install IoTmaxx on location

- 1.4 Connect to the power supply.
- 1.5 Position the device and the antenna optimally for a good mobile signal.

Connect the IoTmaxx to the device - The preferred way of connection is based on the local network, through which we will access devices:

- 1.6 Find the device IP in the network.
- 1.7 Turn ON Modbus TCP service and make config changes (if needed).
- 1.8 Connection should be self-established.

4.3.3 LPC Transformations

The key component of establishing the FCC is the mapping of the Modbus protocol to the IEEE2030.5 standard. In the [Table 4](#) we can observe the mapping between Modbus TCP and IEEE2030.5 in the Austrian pilot.

Table 4: List of transformations performed by the LPC in the Austrian pilot.

IEEE2030.5 type	IEEE2030.5 attribute	description	Modbus section	data point	description
<i>DERstatus</i>	<i>stateOfChargeStatus</i>	SoC measurement	IC124 Basic Storage Control	<i>StorAval</i>	State of charge (ChaState) minus storage reserve (MinRsvPct) times capacity rating (AhrRtg).
<i>DERControlBase</i>	<i>opModTargetW</i>	absolute active power setpoint	l123 Immediate	<i>WMaxLimPct</i>	Set power output to the specified level.

<i>ActivePower</i>	<i>value</i>	active power in watts	l11X Inverter	W	AC Power value
--------------------	--------------	--------------------------	---------------	---	----------------

4.3.4 Demonstration

Finally, we present the screenshots from a use case in the Austrian pilot. Firstly on Figure 20 we can observe the message about the successful installation of Docker on IoTmaxx, and its proper running on Figure 21. From the pictures, we can conclude LPC was operating well in the given environment.

```
root@Gateway:~# docker image ls
REPOSITORY          TAG          IMAGE ID       CREATED        SIZE
ghcr.io/cybergrid-development/lpc 1.2.4       d7688d200bcb  Less than a second ago  570MB
ghcr.io/cybergrid-development/lpc 1.2.3       c386da6bbe59  Less than a second ago  252MB
```

Figure 20: Presentation of installed Docker images (version 1.2.3, 1.2.4) on IoTmaxx.

```
root@Gateway:~# docker ps
CONTAINER ID   IMAGE                                COMMAND                  CREATED        STATUS        PORTS          NAMES
813a79a34838  ghcr.io/cybergrid-development/lpc:1.2.4  "java -jar legacy-pr..."  4 days ago    Up 4 days    8080-8081/tcp  practical_jennings
```

Figure 21: Message about running Docker container 1.2.4 on IoTmaxx.

On Figure 22 setup of a YAML file for use cases with two inverters in one location is shown, which is a unique upgrade done for the Austrian pilot. Such an upgrade was needed in order to create a robust approach that handled different scenarios.

```
1 version: 1.0.0
2 connections:
3   - name: IEEE2030
4     type: NATS
5     host: 10.0.0.1
6     port: 4222
7     reconnect: true
8   - name: ModbusTCPConnection_Inv1
9     type: Modbus
10    host: 192.168.0.123
11    port: 502
12  - name: ModbusTCPConnection_Inv2
13    type: Modbus
14    host: 192.168.0.234
15    port: 502
16  transformations:
```

Figure 22: LPC configuration YAML connection set up to two inverters.

The insight about the transformation of active power data points, which is the primary data point for monitoring direction, happening in LPC, can be inspected on Figure 23.

```
88 - name: active_power_in_watts_Inv1
89   connections:
90     incoming-connection:
91       - ModbusTCPConnection_Inv1
92     incoming-format: JSON
93     outgoing-connection:
94       - IEEE2030
95     outgoing-format: JSON
96   to-outgoing:
97     to-topic: d304b698-f012-4595-b241-21f330cb80cd.devices.{natsId}.attributes.ActivePower.value.monitor
98     message: |-
99       {
100         "ActivePower": {
101           "value": {
102             "lpc:mapping": {
103               "path": "40090",
104               "type": "float32"
105             }
106           }
107         }
108       }
109   interval-request:
110     interval: 5000
111     request:
112       modbus-function-code: 3
113       modbus-device-id: 1
114       modbus-library: java
115       endianness: big-swap
116       modbus-registers:
117         - register-address: 40090
118           type: float32
```

Figure 23: LPC configuration of YAML transformation of monitoring attribute - active power.

4.4 Lessons Learned

The installation of LPC into several REC households in the Austrian pilot has provided valuable insights into the practical challenges and opportunities associated with achieving interoperability in complex energy systems. This section presents the key findings learned from this integration process.

4.4.1 Creating a robust approach

After multiple installations, CyberGrid can highlight the importance of a robust and device-agnostic deployment plan. This, above all, ensures the success of the project as the working hours of an installer make the project too costly for the benefits provided by the energy stored in PV and/or BESS. In addition, creating an implementation plan that a REC member can easily and safely implement himself would increase the project's success chances even further.

4.4.2 Challenges with protocol mappings

Another point to make after implementations in the field is the challenge of using IEEE2030.5 over NATS, as there is we found no device that could communicate via this protocol. Furthermore, translation from Modbus to the new IEEE2030.5 is very difficult as the standards were never thought to be compatible. This is an issue as some data points from IEEE2030.5 cannot be found in Modbus registries, and simultaneously, there might be two options for another data point (e.g. DERControlBase or ActivePower).

5 CONCLUSION

This report documents the software integration activities carried out within the InterSTORE project, focusing on the deployment and adaptation of the Legacy Protocol Converter (LPC) to devices in three pilot sites—Germany, Spain, and Austria. Through detailed documentation of the use cases, involved devices, communication workflows, and integration steps, the report provides a technical reference and a practical guide for future users of the LPC. In these pilots, the LPC enabled conversion from legacy protocols such as Modbus and MQTT into NATS and constructing IEEE 2030.5 compatible messages from custom messages or register readings.

In German pilot, the LPC was integrated into a multi-physics hybrid energy storage system in the Research Centre Jülich. The term “multi-physics” implies that the overall system consists of cross-domain technologies (e.g. heat pumps and thermal energy storage) as well as batteries. The software integration to these devices targeted the joint optimization of different storage technologies according to the energy autarky target of the clustered system consisting of electrical loads, PV generators, batteries, and heat pumps in the campus. In the pilot, a single LPC with multiple transformations was deployed in a Raspberry Pi as a Docker container and it was connected to the campus local area network. This LPC was configured for monitoring the active power consumption of the loads from its PQ meter, the active power injection of the PVs from its SMA Solar Inverter, the state-of-charge of the Riello battery from its inverter, and the state-of-charge of the thermal energy storage unit connected to the Viessmann heat pump from its MQTT adapter; and for controlling the set points of battery and the heat pump. For the monitoring tasks, the *DERStatus* and *MirrorMeteringList* were used as IEEE 2030.5 data models; and for controlling *DERControl*. In Spanish pilot, the LPC was integrated into the AC/DC grid forming converter linked to the battery storage to enable virtual inertia service provision to the grid. The LPC was deployed as a Docker container and implemented Modbus-based power inverter and the IEEE 2030.5-compliant EMS. To monitor the inverter, *DERStatus* model was used, and to control it, *DERControlBase*. The deployment of Docker-based containers streamlined the configuration and operation of the solution, while speed tests validated its efficiency in handling real-time data exchange. In Austrian pilot, the LPC was integrated into inverters of BESS and PVs involved in a renewable energy community. In this integration, the hardware Maxx GW4100 Gateway LTE 4G produced by IoTmaxx hosted the LPC, which enabled transformations from legacy systems’ Modbus registers into standard IEEE2030.5 data models such as *DERstatus*, *DERControlBase*, *ActivePower* to perform tasks such as SOC reading and changing the control set points of the community devices.

All pilots demonstrated successful LPC integration into devices. The pilots showcased low-latency transformation from/to legacy protocols such as MQTT and Modbus while also standardizing custom messages into IEEE 2030.5 data models. The results serve as indicator of potential of the LPC as a key enabler of interoperability in energy systems comprising multiple legacy protocols and non-standardized message formats. On the other hand, the integration efforts in German pilot revealed several challenges, particularly in synchronization of the LPC’s reading from Modbus and MQTT endpoints. As the LPC determines the frequency of reading from Modbus, while lacking such a control for the MQTT interactions, there exist multiple event triggering references in the same ecosystem. During the experiments, the LPC lacked inherent logic to synchronize the timing of reading from a Modbus register with the timing of publishing by an MQTT agent. However, the German pilot overcame this challenge by including a Python software component in the EMS platform that implements a set of conservative rules to ensure that the EMS algorithm consumes near-synchronized inputs. Besides, use case specific solutions, the pilot activities produced know-how that can guide

future implementation of LPC such as the device agnostic deployment plan developed in Austrian pilot.

The lessons learned from all pilots—ranging from temporal synchronization issues to the complexities of adopting the IEEE 2030.5 data model—offer valuable insights for future deployments. The report emphasizes that the LPC can serve as a versatile integration tool on both the device and platform sides of the energy management nexus. In this context, the findings of *D3.3 Report on the Software Tool Integration with Selected Platforms* complement the results of the current report. Therefore, the readers are encouraged to consult these reports for a holistic understanding of LPC deployment strategies.

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